

Comparing Spatial Distributions of Supernovae Classes in Spiral Galaxies

This study explores the spatial distribution of different supernova (SN) classes within spiral galaxies. Spiral arms, rich in localized star formation and generally young stellar populations, serve as valuable age indicators. My primary goal is to compare the distributions of Core Collapse (CC) and type Ia SNe (Ia) relative to spiral arms, aiming to gain insights into the distinctions among their progenitors. Leveraging the extensive and recently published Transient Host Exchange (THEX) database (Qin et al., 2022), that established critical associations between supernova events and their respective hosts. To ensure consistent tracing of spiral arms across various cosmological distances, host galaxies were filtered based on redshift and ellipticity, enhancing the visibility of spiral arm structures. Images were rescaled based on redshift to enable a uniform spatial resolution across all galaxies. The SPiral ARC Finder and Reporter (SpArcFiRe) (Davis & Hayes, 2014) software ensured spiral arm identification. SpArcFiRe is a fully automated software employing pixel-based clustering to locate and characterize spiral arms in images of spiral galaxies, enabling the extraction of detailed structural information. Notably, my findings indicate a differential spatial distribution of SNe within spiral galaxies, particularly when normalized by the radius of the host galaxy. CC events are also more than twice as likely to be situated within spiral arm regions than Ia SNe. This observation suggests that Ia progenitors have had more time to migrate from their formation regions compared to the massive, short-lived CC progenitors. Subsequent studies could explore SN distributions within spiral arms and their proximity to the leading edge, where star formation is believed to take place, providing deeper insights into the characteristics of their progenitors.

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1. Introduction

Multiple studies have explored the intricate connections between different supernova (SN) types and their distribution within host galaxies, aiming to discern associations with stellar populations to estimate progenitor ages (McMillan & Ciardullo, 1996; Aramyan et al., 2016). Investigating SN types as indicators of star formation and their spatial relationships to spiral arms enhances our understanding of SN progenitor characteristics.

Core-collapse (CC) SNe (Types Ib, Ic, and II) result from the gravitational collapse of young massive stellar cores, closely associated with active star-forming regions (Anderson et al. 2012). In contrast SNe Ia arise from thermonuclear explosions of C/O white dwarfs (Maoz & Mannucci 2012). SNe Ia typically lack hydrogen and helium in their spectra, distinguishing them from SNe CC (Wheeler & Harkness, 1990). This distinction implies the likelihood of older progenitors for SNe Ia. The occurrence of SNe Ia in spiral galaxies indicates a significant fraction of their progenitors is

associated with stellar populations of intermediate ages, and they can be considered as weak tracers of star formation (Mannucci et al. 2005; Hakobyan et al. 2011). While observations in elliptical galaxies suggest an older population of low-mass star progenitors for SNe Ia (van den Bergh, 1994; Zhu et al. 2010; Gilfanov & Bogdan, 2011), other studies have hinted at a strong correlation between SN Ia rates and star formation rate, connecting SNe Ia with younger, massive stellar populations (Mannucci et al. 2005; Sullivan et al. 2006). These studies underscore the complexity and uncertainty surrounding the ages of SN Ia progenitors.

Several studies have been done to use positional age indicators to determine the progenitor age of SNe. One of the first studies to apply this technique was the study by Moore (1973), who delved into the positional patterns of 19 SNe within host galaxies. His findings revealed that a majority of SNe are situated at the innermost periphery of spiral arms, and he approximated their lifetimes to be under five million years, coupled with masses surpassing 35 solar masses. Maza & van den Bergh's (1976) study and Bartunov et

al.'s (1994) expanded these insights, indicating a closer proximity of all SNe types to spiral arms compared to a random distribution in discs. McMillan & Ciardullo (1996) and Petrosian et al. (2005) affirmed the tighter clustering of CC SNe around arms than SNe Ia. Finally, Aramyan et al. (2016) used a large sample of 215 SNe to find that CC SNe occur more closely to the leading edge of the spiral arm than Ia events, suggesting younger progenitors. This observation aligns with the notion that more massive stars, characterized by shorter lifetimes, have had less time to travel from their formation sites before undergoing a supernova explosion. However, these studies used diverse methods and inhomogeneous data. In particular, the shape and the edges of the spiral arms were determined visually, which could lead to inconsistencies. Finally, the small sample sizes of these earlier studies limit the statistical significance of the identified correlations.

The Transient Host Exchange (THEx) (Qin et al., 2022) database released in 2021 emerges as a pivotal asset in advancing this area of research, offering the opportunity to significantly increase the sample size of SNe compared to previous studies. The THEx provides a comprehensive repository of extragalactic transients, including SNe, along with their host galaxy properties. Leveraging reported coordinates, redshifts, and, if available, host galaxy information, the THEx team engages in cross-identification to link events with their host galaxies or identify the most probable host candidates from diverse survey catalogs. Simultaneously, THEx compiles comprehensive datasets by extracting photometric, spectroscopic, and derived physical properties of the host galaxies recorded in these catalogs. Covering a vast spectral range from the far ultraviolet to mid-infrared, this expansive database comprises 36 333 unique events, including 18 000 events with newly identified hosts, significantly expanding the diversity and volume of the sample available for analysis.

In this paper, I will investigate the distribution of Ia and CC SNe relative to spiral arms. Building on previous research, I aim to include a larger sample of SNe with homogeneous image quality and consistent identification of spiral arms. To identify candidates for the sample, I made use of the THEx. Leveraging THEx enhances the accuracy of this study by allowing for more informed selection and analysis of SNe, thereby contributing to a more robust understanding of the distribution of Ia and CC SNe relative to spiral arms. With the release of this database, it is possible to significantly increase the sample size of this study. The

goal of this paper is to investigate the spatial distribution of CC and Ia SNe in relation to spiral arms, as they are believed to originate from progenitors spanning different age ranges.

2. Sample selection and Reduction

The study sample was drawn from the THEx. I chose to utilize data from the GALEX (AIS GR6/7; Bianchi et al. 2017) survey for its ultraviolet observations, providing enhanced visibility of bright star-forming regions. The intention was that it would facilitate more effective identification of star formation regions. However, for the final analysis, Legacy Survey images were used due to the 1.4" pixel scale limitation of GALEX, which hindered the clear identification of spiral arms. Subsequent divisions were made through the examination of images obtained for the study, considering the necessity for a well-defined sample and high angular resolution images of the SNe hosts. Starting from the full THEx sample, cuts were implemented based on the distance to the host galaxy and the observed ellipticity of the galaxy, with the assurance that all identified SNe in THEx had available spectroscopic classification and accurate position measurements.

Exclusion criteria were applied to galaxies with a redshift higher than $z=0.025$, as beyond this threshold, accurately distinguishing spiral arms became challenging. This redshift cut aimed to maintain a large and well-resolved sample. Considering the intrinsic brightness differences between Ia and CC SNe, where Ia events are significantly brighter and therefore visible from greater distances, an even distance cut was applied to both events based on spatial resolution. Additional cuts were made based on galaxy ellipticity with $e = 1 - \frac{\text{semi-minor axis}}{\text{semi-major axis}}$ (Bianchi et al. 2017). The set limit of 0.65 was visually determined to ensure clear visibility and identification of spiral arm structures. Elliptical and irregular galaxies were excluded from the sample. The determination of spiral arm structure involved visual assessment using Pan-STARRS1 grz-band images (Chambers et al. 2016) for events in the northern hemisphere and DECaLS DR10 (Dey et al. 2019) images for events in the southern hemisphere. Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the remaining events at each stage following the applied selection criteria.

Table 1. The number of events remaining that meet the specified conditions.

Selection Criterion	Number of events
THEX database	36 333
GALEX-AIS	11 821
Type Ia and Core Collapse	4 681
Ellipticity and Redshift	871
Spiral Galaxies	367
Final Sample	367

After applying these criteria to THEX events, the final sample comprised images of 367 events in 362 host galaxies, encompassing positions for 84 Ia events and 283 CC events.

3. Analysis

For accurate analysis of the SNe and their distance to spiral arms, a central goal of this study is to reduce inhomogeneity in the data. To achieve this, all images utilized in the final analysis were sourced from Legacy Survey DR10 (Dey et al., 2019) in the grz-bands. The mitigation of data inhomogeneity was further addressed by deriving a formula to dynamically resize downloaded images based on redshift. This resizing adjusts the pixel count in the image, by varying the angular scale to keep the physical resolution the same across all host galaxies. This approach ensures that events further away have a higher angular resolution while maintaining a similar physical resolution. A scatterplot of the angular size of the host galaxy against the redshift was plotted and a linear fit was applied. To ensure complete coverage and prevent any parts of the galaxies from being cut off in the images, the linear fit was deliberately shifted upward. This adjustment, depicted in Figure 1. This formula was used to scale the pixel height and width of the FITS files according to redshift for the image download.

For the consistent and accurate identification of spiral arms in the galaxy images, the SPiral ARm FINDER and REporter (SpArcFiRe) (Davis & Hayes, 2014) software tool played a crucial role. The tool processes an approximately centered image of a spiral galaxy, identifying, centering, and sizing the galaxy while allowing for the masking of nearby stars and objects. Subsequently, the tool enhances the image contrast and detects spiral arms through pixel-based clustering. It automatically extracts detailed structural information about the spiral arms, listing pixels within each arm segment and performing a least-squares fit of a logarithmic spiral arc. The steps in identifying spiral arms are depicted in figure 2. This process generates

Figure 1. The distribution of galaxy size in arcseconds compared to their redshift. Overlaid is the linear fit to this data. The dotted line represents the linear fit shifted up to ensure the complete visibility of each galaxy in the images.

per-arc parameters, including pitch angle and arm segment length, producing quantitative measures that facilitate an objective analysis of spiral galaxies.

Importantly, SpArcFiRe successfully identified spiral arms for all galaxies within the sample. The tool generates a reprojected mask of the spiral arm structure, which was used to determine whether events were located inside or outside the arms and facilitated the calculation of the minimum distance to the nearest spiral arm. By converting right ascension and declination to pixel coordinates through the FITS file's world coordinate data, each event's location was compared to the mask. For events outside a marked region, the separation to the nearest point of a spiral arm was calculated, see figure 3, and translated back to an angular distance, subsequently converted to physical separation through the host galaxy's spectroscopically confirmed distance. Using the coordinates of the host galaxy and the event, the distance to the galactic center was also calculated to compare the radial distribution of each event.

4. Results

The comprehensive analysis of the 367 SNe in the sample reveals intriguing patterns in their distribution. In this sample, 148 events were located within spiral arms, while 219 were situated in interarm regions. A notable trend emerges when considering the distribution of event types within and between spiral arms, particularly highlighting the prevalence of CC SNe in these environments. Of the 283 observed CC SNe, a significant portion, 131 events (46.3%), were found within spiral arms. In contrast, the distribution for

Figure 2. The stepwise image processing conducted by the SpArcFiRe tool. The top-left presents the original input image, while the top-right showcases the reoriented version of the image. In the middle-left, the high-contrast processed image is depicted. The middle-right displays the fitted spiral arm mask, and the bottom-right exhibits the spiral mask overlaid on the reoriented image. Finally, the bottom-left portrays the reprojected spiral arm in the same view as the input image. In all images the event location is indicated, SN2012W.

Figure 3. The position of transient SN2015at and the distance to the nearest spiral arm indicated in white, 0.92686".

Ia SNe shows a different pattern, with only 17 out of 84 events (20.2%) located inside spiral arms. A detailed breakdown of their positions relative to the spiral arms for each class is provided in table 2. Additionally, to validate the robustness of the results, the analysis was replicated using an equivalent sample size by randomly selecting CC events and comparing them to the Ia events. The consistent findings reinforce the observed differences in spatial distributions between the two SN classes.

Table 2. The distribution of Ia and CC events relative to the spiral arms.

Event	Total events	Events inside spiral arm	Percentage (%)
Ia	84	17	20.2
CC	283	131	46.3
Total	367	148	40.3

To delve deeper into the radial distribution within host galaxies, an analysis of each SN class was conducted, normalizing the distance between the event and the galactic center to account for variations in galaxy size. There appears to be no substantial difference in the radial distribution of events based on their distances and normalized distances to the galaxy. CC SNe tend to occur slightly closer to the galactic center than Ia events, as depicted in figure 4. To analyze the distribution of the different types of SNe relative to the spiral arms the distances were also normalized to the size of the host galaxies. This normalization eliminates variations based on the actual size of the galaxy, facilitating a focused examination. In the non-normalized distribution, both Ia and CC events exhibit a close association with spiral arms. However, when considering the normalized scale, a subtle yet discernible difference emerges—CC SNe display a tighter distribution around the spiral arms compared to Ia SNe. This nuanced contrast is visually depicted in figure 5, while table 3 provides a consolidated summary of the mean distance to the nearest spiral arm for each class, accompanied by their respective standard deviations. These findings contribute to a refined understanding of the spatial characteristics of different SN classes in relation to spiral arms and the radial distribution within host galaxies.

Table 3. The mean distance and standard deviation of the distance to the nearest spiral arms.

Event	Mean distance (kpc)	Standard deviation	Number of events outside spiral arm
Ia	2.68	4.81	67
CC	2.49	3.83	152

Figure 4. On the right side, the figure illustrates the probability density function of the distance to galactic center, displaying both non-normalized and normalized (bottom). The left side presents the cumulative density function of the distance to the nearest spiral arm, with representations of both non-normalized (top) and normalized (bottom).

Figure 5. On the right side, the figure illustrates the probability density function of the distance to the nearest spiral arm, displaying both non-normalized and normalized (bottom). The left side presents the cumulative density function of the distance to the nearest spiral arm, with representations of both non-normalized (top) and normalized (bottom).

To further explore the distinction between the distributions of Ia and CC SNe, I conducted the 2-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test and the 2-sample Anderson-Darling (AD) test. These tests, KS for its sensitivity to differences in both location and shape of cumulative distribution functions and AD for its emphasis on differences in distribution tails, shed light on the dissimilarity between the Ia and CC progenitor populations. The KS test yielded a statistic of 0.2605 with a p-value of 0.0002, while the AD test produced a statistic of 12.7477 with a p-value of 0.001 (table 4). These results underscore a significant difference between the distributions, highlighting that the progenitors of Ia and CC SNe likely originate from distinct populations. Notably, most of this dissimilarity is driven by events located inside spiral arms with a separation of 0. Excluding these events from the analysis led to a notable shift, with the tests no longer rejecting the null hypothesis (KS-statistic 0.0920, $p=0.7829$ and AD-statistic 0.3889, $p>0.25$).

Table 4. An overview of the results from the statistical tests comparing the distribution of Ia and CC events.

Test	Statistic	Probability
KS	0.2605	0.0002
AD	12.7477	0.001

These results suggest that Ia progenitors are older than their CC counterparts, since they have had more time to migrate away from the spiral arms. This is especially apparent in the distribution of events inside and outside of these regions. Although the distribution outside of the spiral arms is close between each class, CC SNe are more closely tied to their spiral arms.

5. Discussion

The results presented above warrant a comprehensive analysis to fully interpret their implications within the context of the spatial distribution of SNe within spiral galaxies. Although there appears to be a discernible difference in the distribution of each class of events concerning the spiral arms, this disparity seems less pronounced than expected based on the distribution of events inside and outside the spiral arms. An important consideration in this analysis is that the distance to the nearest spiral arms was measured, not necessarily indicating that the SN progenitor originated from that specific spiral arm. Additionally, it is crucial to note that the analysis did not measure the location within spiral arms relative to the star-forming regions. To refine our understanding of the spatial distribution relative to the

spiral arms, accounting for the rotation of the galaxy and disk stars would be crucial in determining the specific origin of each progenitor.

It's noteworthy that, although a cut was applied to the ellipticity of host galaxies, this factor was not considered in calculating the distances between the SNe and the host galaxies and the spiral arms. This omission could potentially contribute to a less distinct distribution of different events. It is worth mentioning that employing Integral Field Unit (IFU) spectroscopy allows for the measurement of velocities of various parts of the galaxy along our line of sight. This information can be utilized to estimate the galaxy's inclination and correct for it, providing more accurate distances for a more refined analysis.

Furthermore, an interesting avenue for exploration involves comparing the distributions of these events to a randomly generated disk population of stars. Such a comparison, previously conducted by McMillan & Ciardullo in 1996, demonstrated that Type Ia events are likely to have older progenitors than CC SNe. Applying this process to our expanded sample of SNe could provide valuable insights into the progenitor ages of Type Ia SNe.

The utilization of data from a single survey within the THEx underscores the potential for enhancing the sample size by applying similar methods to multiple surveys within the THEx. This expanded dataset would contribute to greater statistical significance in our analyses.

Additionally, it's worth noting that THEx has consolidated hosts for rarer classes of SNe. This same analysis could be extended to identify very young or very old explosions for the first time, broadening the scope of insights gained from this study. The comprehensive dataset provided by THEx offers opportunities to explore and understand various subclasses of SNe in the context of their host galaxies.

My findings indicate that, although SNs II exhibit a more pronounced correlation with spiral arms than SNs Ia, both types of SNe tend to occur in close proximity to the spiral arms. However, SNs Ia are distributed slightly more loosely than SNs CC, suggesting that the progenitors of SNs Ia have had more time to disperse from their formation sites and integrate with the overall stellar population. Consequently, the progenitors of SNe Ia arise from a population that is sufficiently old to migrate away from their birthplaces during their lifetimes, representing the distribution of the older stellar population. This finding aligns with theories of SN CC formation from massive star

evolution and observations that SNs CC tend to occur near star formation regions.

6. Conclusion

This study explored potential correlations between the spatial distribution of SN events and spiral arms, emphasizing a rigorous approach to sample selection for meaningful comparisons. Leveraging the THEx not only facilitated a larger sample size than previous studies but also ensured homogeneity in the dataset for robust analyses. Consistent identification of spiral arms in host galaxies was achieved through the application of the SpArcFiRe tool, enhancing the accuracy of my findings.

The results reveal a distinct pattern in the spatial distribution of CC SNe, indicating a pronounced association with and prevalence inside spiral arms. In stark contrast, Type Ia SNe exhibit a more dispersed distribution outside of spiral arms and are notably less likely to occur within them. This discrepancy suggests that CC events are strongly linked to spiral arms, reflecting the influence of their progenitors, which are likely young massive stars. On the other hand, the spatial characteristics of Type Ia SNe point to a more scattered distribution, implying progenitors sourced from older stellar populations, ranging from intermediate to old ages.

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